

All My Sons: A Classic Essence of Broadway Entertainment

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Broadway remains an integral part of American entertainment. There are currently forty-one professional theatres in this district, acting as the American counterpart to the British West End theatre in London. The majority of Broadway plays are musicals, and this remains the norm till date.

The 1940s are considered as the Golden Age of American Musical theatre. The plays offered a true sense of Americana that resonated with the average citizen looking for entertainment. In the period of the World War II, the average American would search for a distraction to escape the brutal reality of war and bloodshed that gripped most of the world, and Broadway provided that escape. However, musicals weren't the only genre that gained popularity at this time. Thanks in no small part to the works of playwright Eugene O'Neill, serious contemporary drama became popular as well. Successful plays of the era included two that were penned by Tennessee Williams: *The Glass Menagerie* (1945-46) and *A Streetcar Named Desire* (1948).

As World War II approached, in addition to cheery escapist musicals, there were also several serious plays that dealt with the war itself. These plays focused on themes such as Nazism and American non-intervention. One of the pioneers for this type of play was Lillian Hellman's *Watch on the Rhine*.

In the post-war period, there was a sharp increase in demand for Broadway shows and movies. In spite of this, the number of plays steadily decreased until becoming almost negligible in the time of The Great Depression. Other successful plays of this era include *Anne Lucasta* which had 950 performances and *Song of Norway* which had 860 performances. Arthur Miller's *All My Sons* falls into the category of post-war drama that deals with wartime experiences. This genre proved quite popular; other successful plays dealing with this genre included *Mister Roberts*, *Command Decision* and most notably 'South Pacific.

Noted playwright Arthur Miller (October 17, 1915 – February 10, 2005) is considered an iconic playwright and figure in American theatre. In addition to his controversial plays, he is also remembered for his eventful and turbulent marriage to Hollywood starlet Marilyn Monroe. His plays combined social awareness with a searching concern for his characters' inner lives. Miller's very first play *The Man Who Had All the Luck* failed miserably on Broadway, but his career soon gained momentum with his subsequent plays.

In addition to *All My Sons*, Miller wrote *Death of a Salesman*, one of his most successful plays and an iconic play in American theatre. This play was both commercially successful and critically acclaimed. One of his most memorable and controversial works is 'The Crucible' (1953). The play is a direct result of Miller's experiences with the House Un-American Activities Committee (HUAC) which accused him of promoting Communism with his anti-American themes in his popular plays, *The Crucible* deals with the Salem witch trials, and Miller draws a parallel with his own persecution at the hands of the HUAC.

Miller's *All My Sons* had its debut staging at the Coronet Theatre in New York City on January 29, 1947. Becoming wildly successful, it ran for 328 performances. It went on to win great accolades, winning the New York Drama Critics Circle Award, and the Tony Awards for Best Actor and Best Direction.' It was revived in 1987 on April 22nd at the John Golden Theatre; this won the Tony Award for Best Revival of a Play. It was revived yet again on October 16, 2008, at the Gerald Schoenfeld theatre.

The story of the play is rooted in reality. Miller has said that he based it on the events he read in an Ohio newspaper: a munitions manufacturer knowingly shipped out defective parts for tanks. These had suffered mechanical failures which had led to the deaths of many soldiers. In *All My Sons*, Miller examines the morality of the man who gives more importance to the immediate rewards that will satisfy his family in the short term rather than the consequences his actions would have on those who are dependent on him. He also chose to write a problem play that was influenced by Henrik Ibsen's work, particularly *The Wild Duck*.

The story takes place over the course of a day, several years after the completion of World War II, with flashbacks dating back to the wartime days. It is set primarily in the house of the Kellers. The play begins when Ann Deever visits her current boyfriend, Chris Keller. On the night of the visit, a storm knocks over a tree in his family's yard. This tree was planted in honour of the Keller's late son, Larry, a pilot who died in World War II. The timing seems significant to Chris's mother Kate, who still thinks of Ann as Larry's girlfriend, not Chris's. Kate still believes that Larry is alive, and insists that Ann feels the same, but Ann makes it clear that she isn't waiting for Larry. Upon hearing this, Joe is shattered at the repercussions of his actions. He realizes that the twenty one pilots who died were, in a way, his sons, and he was responsible for their deaths. He volunteers to surrender, but instead goes to his room and shoots himself.

Miller's willingness to follow the conventions of Greek tragedy is seen. In Greek plays such as those by Aeschylus, and in the tragedies of Shakespeare several centuries later, the protagonist is a fine, upstanding man with one notable tragic flaw that leads to his downfall. Joe Keller is seen as the quintessential American breadwinner, a very ordinary man, decent, hard-working and charitable. But, like the protagonist of the ancient drama, he has a flaw or weakness- his unwillingness to commit to his responsibilities. This, in turn, causes him to act wrongly. When faced with the magnitude of what he has done, he is forced to accept responsibility. He realizes how his actions, which were done with the welfare of his family in mind, leads to the death of his son and other innocent pilots. His suicide is necessary to restore the moral order of the universe, and allow his other son Chris to live freely without guilt.

Flavours of Literature

The tree that was planted in memory of Larry by the Kellers carries great symbolic significance. The tree was planted, even though Kate never gave up hope that Larry might return alive. When the play begins, the tree is found shorn in half by the wind in August, the same month Larry was born.

The setting of the play in post-war America provides the major emotional backdrop of the play. The sacrifices a soldier goes through, and the emotional turmoil faced by his family is something that resonates with all of us.

Chris is a definite idealist; we can compare him and his conflict with his father with the character of Wesley Tate in Sam Sheppard's *Curse of the Starving Class*, a tale similarly set in post-war America. Wesley, though more wound tight than Chris, wishes for harmony of a family that is falling apart, and his idealism gets radically shaken as the plot progresses. Chris' emotional response against his father when he says that he did what he did to provide a good future in business for his son, goes as such as, 'Yet we cannot stand in judgement of Joe and brand him an evil man. We can only pity him for his short-sightedness and unwillingness to take responsibility for his own actions. His angry speech when confronted by Chris is an example of his mind set that says "I did what I could, under the circumstances." "What should I do? ... Jail? You want me to go to jail? If you want me to go, say so! Is that where I belong? Then tell me so! (Slight pause) What's the matter, why can't you tell me? ... I'll tell you why you can't say it. In the end, the weight of his guilt becomes too much to bear and he takes his own life. The words of Kate at the end, when Chris is blaming himself for his father's suicide, is an excellent ending to the play. She says, "Don't, dear. Don't take it on yourself. Forget now. Live." This not only proves she has come to terms with both Larry's death and Joe's guilt, but also that she doesn't wish the cycle of guilt to continue. She wishes that Chris marry Ann and lead a peaceful life away from this terrible legacy.

In conclusion, it is observed that the plot and setting reflect the sentiments of working-class people whose lives have been altered by the Second World War. Theatre, especially tragedy, is meant to cause purgation of emotion. While musicals formed the 'escapism' side of theatre, works such as those of Miller and Williams helped audiences resonate with the reality of what was happening around them. In that sense, 'All My Sons' is a hard-hitting play that is essentially American.

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